

**Effects of human resource development practices on service quality of services offshore
outsourcing firms**

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Abstract

Purpose- To investigate the influence of human resource development practices on the quality of service of services offshore outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and 402 respondents who fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study responded. To examine the hypothesized relationships structural equation modeling with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16.

Findings- The analysis yielded two component factor structure for human resource development practices, which were termed as talent engagement and job related training. It was found that both talent engagement and job related training significantly positively predict the quality of service. The study provided empirical data to support the contention that organizations should develop and engage capabilities of employees to enhance the quality of service.

Originality/value- Characteristics of service business demand the effective use of human resource. Therefore, it is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information for academics and practitioners to make informed decisions on the influence of human resource development practices on the quality of service.

Keywords: human resource development practices, quality of service, services offshore outsourcing, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Service industry has witnessed a rapid growth during the past few decades not only in the industrialized economies but also in less developed and emerging economies (Redondo-Cano and Canet-Giner, 2010; Reed and Storrud-Barnes, 2009). The literature also provides evidence for the internationalization of services (Akehurst, 2008; Javalgi and Martin, 2007; Jones and Crick, 2001). Due to the internationalization of sourcing services, on the one hand, there is an increase in firms relying on services obtained from overseas markets (Jones and Crick, 2001). On the other hand, more and more services firms from developing countries competing to offer variety of services such as legal and medical research from their offshore locations (Akehurst, 2008; Javalgi and Martin, 2007).

Offshore outsourcing occurs when “one firm delegates responsibility of performing a function or series of tasks to another firm, and when the second firm is based in another country, outsourcing becomes offshoring” (World Bank, 2006, p.5). Dramatic improvements in information and telecommunications technologies (ICT) and decreasing costs of data transmission have extended the number of services that could be outsourced such as legal and medical research, risk assessment, engineering and design, and market research. Hence, services offshore outsourcing now encompasses a wide array of export-oriented services spanning the entire value chain. Outsourcing of services has become important as means of maximizing flexibility and control and forming strategic alliances (Lacity et al., 1995). On the one hand, outsourcing allows foreign client firms to make strategic decisions regarding which resources and capabilities are to be developed inside the firm and which are to be outsourced and to be relied on specialized suppliers (Espino-Rodríguez and Padro'n-Robaina, 2006; Redondo-Cano and Canet-Giner, 2010). On the other hand, the supply of offshore outsourced services has become a popular business strategy of developing countries to leapfrog the industrial development stage (World Bank, 2006).

According to the World Bank (2006, pp. 8-12), more than 150 countries are competing to offer offshore outsourced services but some of the most attractive services outsourcing

destinations are China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Philippines, Thailand, and Sri Lanka. Although the cost of service offering is an important factor in attracting offshore businesses, it is not the only criterion that clients consider in making site selection (World Bank, 2006, pp. 20-29). The heightened competition between these countries in the provision of offshore services suggest the need of providing quality services to stand out from the rest in order to compete (e.g. Bartlett and Ghoshal, 1987). This implies the importance of effective use of human resource in service provision (Akehurst, 2008).

In the above context, the specific aim of this paper is to investigate the effects of human resource development (HRD) practices on the quality of service of offshore outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka. Investigating HRD practices of services offshore outsourcing industry is important for several reasons. First, the literature on services industry identifies the importance of understanding factors that affect services firms' competitive and international advantage (Javalgi and Martin, 2007). Advancements in ICT made it easier and faster to outsource numerous services overseas spanning the entire value chain by taking the advantage of lower costs and broader talent pools around the world (World Bank, 2006). In this context, offshore outsourcing firms have to learn how to satisfy a highly diverse international customer base for sustained competitive advantage (Ueltschy et al., 2007). Hence, it is important to better understand drivers that enhance firms' quality of service offerings when competing internationally, especially, in technology-based offshore services sectors (Essén, 2009; Javalgi and Martin, 2007).

Second, services offshore outsourcing firms like many other service sectors use project-based temporary work structures and associated temporary work processes to deliver highly differentiated and customised products and services to its customers (Turner et al., 2008). Due to these features, services offshore outsourced firms can be identified as an organizational innovation, which influence both technical and social system of organizations through new structures, methods, technical systems, and behavioural patterns (Martinsuo et al., 2006). However, the literature suggest that these firms generally lack organizational resources that underpin the operation of an internal labour market, and the provision of sustainable long-term

employment relationship poses challenges for people management (Walsh and Deery, 2006). In this context, HRD is very much relevant to this sector in improving the quality of service delivery. Therefore, there is a need to clearly apprehend the effects of investment in human resource in enhancing the quality of service provision in this sector.

Third, although Asia provides a very unique dynamic business environment for offshore outsourcing of services, it suffers from severe skill shortages in both manufacturing and services sectors (Zheng, 2009). Hence, services firms have to compete not only with one another but also with increasingly rejuvenating manufacturers for the best talent (Gardner, 2005; Zheng, 2009). As a consequence, services firms in Asia are faced with the challenging task of keeping talent for their continuous growth and expansion (Zheng, 2009). In this regard, Gollan (2005) states that HRD could provide a platform to create success for organizations as well as employees. Nafukho et al. (2004) state that HRD should be positioned within the context of the knowledge economy, and should pursue research that demonstrates the influence of HRD on organisations in the knowledge economy (Nafukho et al., 2004, p. 550). This implies the need of empirical studies investigating effects of HRD in creating competitive and international advantage for services firms in competing for global markets. The present study attempts to address this gap by investigating the effects of HRD on the quality of service of services offshore outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka. The research setting is both progressive and international in nature as the study investigated a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in the global environment. The findings of the study would provide new insights to academics and practitioners alike at a time of increasing international competition, regionalization, industry restructuring and globalization. Further, the findings would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Human resource development practices

Human resource development, according to Chalofsky's (1992, p. 179), increases the learning capacity of individuals and organizations through the development and application of learning-based interventions for the purpose of optimizing human and organizational growth and effectiveness. Further, Harrison and Kessels (2004) identify HRD as a process of individual and group learning which comprises of skilful planning and facilitation of a variety of formal and informal learning and knowledge processes that can enhance organisational progress and individual potential through the development of competence, adaptability, and collaboration. Furthermore, Hamlin and Stewart (2011) perceive HRD as any process that enables individuals, groups, organisations or host systems to learn, develop and change behaviour for the purpose of enhancing their competence, effectiveness, performance and growth.

Previous studies had empirically shown the importance of HRD in creating a desirable work environment, recognising and valuing employees and their work, and providing opportunities for employee advancement (Bassi and McMurrer, 2008, 2007 and 2005; Pickett, 2005; Rauch et al., 2005). In this regard, several researchers emphasized the importance of evaluating human resource within the context of job mobility and employee succession (e.g. Gardner, 2005; Wezel et al., 2006). Therefore, human resource planning, recruitment, selection and allocation can be identified as important human resource management practices connected to HRD that deliver value to the business (Brush and Ruse, 2005; Zula and Chermack, 2007). Overall, when managed effectively, investments in human resource contributes to increase the value of human resource (Berntson et al., 2006), which in turn contributes to positive outcomes of organizations and can become a major source of competitive advantage (Huselid et al., 1997; Le Blanc et al., 2000).

In the context of services firms, irrespective of the business activity services sector firms rely on knowledge workers' capabilities to be productive and to continually create value (Bitner and Brown, 2006; Dickson et al., 2011; Maglio et al., 2006). For instance, Bitner and Brown (2006) state that employees attached to services firms can be used as a sustainable form of differentiation because their intellectual capital can be leveraged to create tailored services for

clients. Therefore, HRD is very important in creating value to services firms (Dickson et al., 2011; Harris, 2009; Tome', 2011). In the specific context of ICT-based service provision, previous studies emphasised the need of employees well equipped with capabilities not only in solid technical competence but also in business knowledge, good communication skills, and effective people skills to better understand business, technology, people, and cultures (Dickson et al., 2011; Harris, 2009; Madhavan and Grover, 1998). In this regard, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2005, p. 4) states "HRD is especially important to services firms, given their high reliance on highly skilled and highly educated workers, as well as indications that a lack of highly skilled personnel is a major impediment to service innovation in most OECD economies". However, despite of the growing number of jobs in services sector, Bitner and Brown (2008) identify situations where services sector employees were not provided with purposefully designed development opportunities. In this regard, previous studies imply that human resource specialists must address criticisms directed at their work not only with regard to how HRD contributes to shape employees' behaviour and attitudes in such a way to make them consistent with organizational goals (e.g. Rauch et al., 2005) but also how HRD contributes to corporate performance (e.g. Bassi and McMurrer, 2007; Nafukho et al., 2004; Pickett, 2005).

Quality of service

Zeithaml (1988) defined the quality of service as a person's evaluation of the "overall excellence or superiority of the service" (p. 3). Therefore, the perceived quality of service is a form of attitude, resulting from the comparison of expectations with the perception of performance (see Bennett and Barkensjo, 2005; Kang, 2006). The literature suggests that the quality of service can be measured in terms of self evaluation, peer evaluation, supervisory evaluation and consumer evaluation (Behrman and Perreault, 1982). For the current study, the quality of service has been operationalized in terms of employees' perception of their own service quality. Several previous studies have also operationalised the quality of service in terms of employees'

perception towards their own service delivery (such as Boshoff and Tait, 1996; Mukherjee and Malhotra, 2006; Schneider et al., 1980). According to Steers and Porter (1991) employees' perception towards the quality of service is a challenge because their perception drives their behaviour. Therefore, several researchers emphasised the importance of managing the perception of employees' of their own service performance (e.g. Mukherjee and Malhotra, 2006).

Further, Shemwell et al. (1998) state that the perception of service quality develops over time, not from a single encounter, and each of a series of contacts with the service provider revealing service provider's abilities. Hence, the quality of service may have many dimensions (Grönroos, 1990; Parasuraman et al., 1985; Silvestro et al., 1988). For instance, Grönroos (1990) identified two dimensions, namely functional (or process) and technical (or outcome). Functional dimension focuses on "how" and concerns interactions that take place during a service delivery such as the speed of service; technical dimension focuses on "what" and concerns what a customer actually receives from a service or a service encounter. A majority of previous studies investigated service quality through SERVQUAL instrument (Parasuraman et al., 1985), which has five dimensions of service delivery, namely, reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness. Fitzgerald *et al.* (1991) also identified several dimensions of quality of service as reliability, responsiveness, aesthetics/appearance, cleanliness/tidiness, comfort, friendliness, communication, courtesy, competence, access, availability, and security. Rust and Oliver (1994) suggested three-dimensions for the evaluation of a service encounter, namely customer-employee interaction, service environment, and outcomes. Therefore, there is no consensus on the exact dimensions of service quality in the literature (Brady and Cronin, 2001).

Al-Hawari et al. (2009) emphasised the importance of human element in the context of service quality. According to Al-Hawari et al. (2009, p. 457), "... employees have an important effect on customer service as they are the key element that customers interact with during the service encounter stage. Well trained employees are able to achieve high level of customer

cognition as well as affection towards the organisation they are dealing with". Since, the quality of service is a result of human interaction between the employees of service provider and its customers, the present study investigated the effect of HRD practices on employees' perception of quality of service that they deliver (and not the expectations). Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1. HRD practices will be positively related to quality of service.

Methodology

Sample

The list of services offshore outsourcing firms was obtained from the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI), which is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. It is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all the BOI registered firms should export at least 90% of their output. Therefore, the BOI registered services outsourcing firms provide at least 90% of their work for offshore client firms. Offshore outsourcing sector in Sri Lanka has increased considerably over the last two decades and employs about 30,000 workforce (LIRNEasia 2006; Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2007). Some of the services these firms provide are intellectual property research, legal and medical research, R&D, equity research, and risk assessment and management, engineering and design, animation, market research, network consultancy and management, and content development.

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. To ease the data collection, contact persons were identified at each firm. The contact persons together with the author of this paper randomly selected employees who were knowledgeable to participate in the survey. In doing so, people who were fulltime employed in their present workplace during the last three years were selected. Since this industrial sector is reputed for having a flat organization structure (Wickramasinghe, 2009), respondents were represented by employees belonged to middle and top layers of the firms and knowledgeable to provide required data for the study. Further, as detailed at the bottom of this section, all the respondents

had Bachelor's degrees or postgraduate degrees related to their job role as their highest level of education. All the respondents were directly involved in services offshore outsourced job tasks in the areas such as intellectual property research, legal and medical research, R&D, equity research, and risk assessment and management, engineering and design, animation, market research, network consultancy and management, and content development. It should be noted that previous studies provide evidence for high labour turnover in this sector (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Hence, respondents may have a small number of years of experience in their present workplaces although they may have several years of service in the industry as a whole. In total, 402 responses were received within four weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. With regard to the demographics of respondents, 53% were male and 47% were female. All the respondents belonged to the age range of 24 to 36 years. 66% of the respondents had Bachelor's degrees or equivalent qualifications and 34% had postgraduate degrees as the highest level of education. The mean tenure in the present workplace was 4 years (S.D. = 1.71).

Measures

Human resource development practices were measured by 12 items from Bassi and McMurrer (2005). Responses for these 12 items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The quality of service was measured from the perception of employees on their service delivery by using 11 items that were generated during the preliminary inquiries made in Sri Lanka and the available literature (such as Fitzgerald *et al.*, 1991; Kang, 2006; Mukherjee and Malhotra, 2006; Parasuraman *et al.*, 1985; Silvestro *et al.*, 1988). Responses for all these 11 items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) very low to (5) very high.

Three firm characteristics (i.e., firm size, ownership, and the years of industry presence) and four individual demographic characteristics (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and education) were controlled. Firm size was assessed by the number of full-time employees in the organisation. Ownership of the firm was binary coded where 0 = sole ownership and 1 = local and foreign

partnership. Industry presence was assessed by the number of years that the firm is in operation. Age and firm tenure were measured in years. Gender (0 = female and 1 = male) and the highest level of educational qualification (0 = Bachelor's degree or equivalent and 1 = Postgraduate degree) were binary coded. The values for age, the years of experience in the present workplace, the number of employees in the firm, and the years of industry presence were log transformed.

Methods of data collection and data analysis

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. The questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector, 1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Cronbach's alpha reliability of the scales was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. In doing so, the criteria recommended by Hair et al. (2006) were adhered to, i.e., eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the

loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7.

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and path analysis were used test the relationships hypothesised. For the path analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16.

Results and discussion

Human resource development practices

The 12-item measure of HRD practices had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.824. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 62% (62.38) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 1. Factor 1 was labelled as "talent engagement" and Factor 2 as "job related training". To understand the nature of distribution of variables, probability-probability plots (P-P plot) were created comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function of each variable with the standard normal distribution function. Figure 1 shows P-P plot of talent engagement while Figure 2 shows P-P plot of job related training. Figure 1 and Figure 2 suggest that both talent engagement and job related training are normally distributed along the fitted lines.

Take in Table 1

Take in Figure 1

Take in Figure 2

Quality of service

The 11-item measure of quality of service had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.868. Principal component factor analysis yielded a single factor, which explained 65% (64.7) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 2. Figure 3 shows P-P plot of quality of service. As can be seen in Figure 3, the variable is normally distributed along the fitted line.

Take in Table 2

Take in Figure 3

Relationship between HRD practices and quality of service

Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations between the variables are shown in Table 3. For instance, it is apparent from Table 3 that talent engagement has a significant positive relationship with the quality of service.

Take in Table 3

In the preliminary stages of SEM, three firm characteristics and four individual demographic characteristics mentioned above were entered as controls. Since none of these variables were significant, in the process of purifying the SEM model, these controls were subsequently removed. The final structural model achieved a good level of fit having CMIN/df = 5.82, GFI = 0.89, CFI = 0.91, and RMSEA=0.05. The summary of analysis is provided in Table 4.

Take in Table 4

The results shown in Table 4 reveal that talent engagement and job related training have significant positive effect on the quality of service. Figure 4 and 5 show these relationships graphically using partial regression plots, which depict the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable when more than one independent variable is in the model. The coefficient of determination (squared multiple correlation) of .358 for the quality of service suggests that these two practices account for 36% of the variation of the quality of service. This supports H1.

Take in Figure 4

Take in Figure 5

Conclusions and implications

While the notion of HRD have been argued to lay at the core of business success the literature reviewed earlier suggests that links between HRD practices and the quality of service have been prescriptive and requires empirical attention. The current study examined the effect of HRD practices on the quality of service of services offshore outsourcing firms.

It was found that HRD practices can broadly be classified into two, namely, practices relating to talent engagement and job related training. Both talent engagement and job related training have significant positive effect on the quality of service. Therefore, the results of the analysis provide empirical evidence for significant positive effect of HRD practices on the quality of service. Although it is very rare to find previous empirical studies conducted in the service

industry or offshore outsourced sector that investigated in detail the links proposed in this study to make straight forward comparisons, in general, the findings support previous studies that talent engagement creates positive results in organisations (such as Bassi and McMurrer, 2005; Pickett, 2005; Zula and Chermack, 2007). The findings also support previous studies that suggested an organisation's efforts to increase its human capabilities through job related training create positive results in organisations (such as Bassi and McMurrer, 2005; Skaggs and Youndt, 2004).

The findings of the study have both theoretical and managerial implications. With regard to the contribution of the study to the existing body of literature, both academics and practitioners need valid information to make informed decisions on talent engagement and job related training on the quality of service, which is desired to be achieved by organisations. Quantitative studies of HRD practices and its influence on quality are not widely reported in the literature. Hence, study makes a considerable contribution to the existing body of literature. Further, since past studies that resemble the current study are very limited, the links proposed in this study could be tested over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts.

With regard to managerial implications, the alignment of talent engagement and job related training with the quality of service may enhance the contribution of human resource to organisational success. Organisations can use the measures proposed in this study to inquire the status of their practices. This will provide practitioners with immediate and practical benefits to know the current status and to make strategies to enhance the relationship. However, as the environment within which organisations operate change over time, ongoing assessment may become essential.

In addition, in today's globally competitive business environment, there is a need for human resource departments to become strategic business partners. Effective HRD can be considered as an essential step towards this direction. The findings also imply that offshore service organisations may be able to retain experienced and skilful employees through talent

engagement and job related training. Therefore, it is important for organisations to have a clear policy to encourage and recognize employees for their contribution to organisational success.

Finally, it should be noted that this research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. Yet, as detailed in the section on *methods of data collection and analysis* every attempt have been made to minimise the common method bias. Future research studies in different samples that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data are necessary to validate the links proposed in this study. In such studies, questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

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Tables

Table 1. Summary of results: factor analysis – HRD practices

	Talent engagement	Job related training
My organisation has highly effective systems and processes in place for managing employees' performance and talent.	.842	
Whenever possible, my organisation seeks to fill vacancies with qualified internal candidates.	.823	
In my organisation, employees have formal development plans in place.	.817	
My organisation has systems in place that help to retain good performers.	.792	
My organisation constantly identifies key performers by continually evaluating their performance.	.778	
My organisation is good at recognizing accomplishments and achievements of employees.	.764	
In my organisation, employees are well trained on work processes.		.856
My organisation constantly makes job related training a priority.		.788
My organisation constantly evaluates the effectiveness of training programmes provided for employees.		.761
Training programmes provided to employees were relevant to their job tasks.		.745
My organisation has a system that provides information to make decisions regarding training programmes.		.743
My organisation orients new employees to their job positions.		.728
Explained variation	42.95	19.43
Eigenvalue	3.32	1.56
Cronbach's alpha	.739	.748

Table 2. Summary of results: factor analysis – quality of service

	Quality of service
My organization has employees who deal with customers in a caring fashion.	.813
My organization is always ready to respond to customer's requests.	.810
When a customer has a problem, my organization provides the customer with individual attention.	.801
My organization ensures customers to feel safe in their transactions with it.	.794
My organization has knowledgeable employees to serve the customers.	.793
My organization can understand the specific needs of its customers.	.792
In my organization, employees give customers individual attention.	.785
When problems occur, my organization gives them the attention in an effort to solve those speedily.	.774
My organization provides prompt service to customers.	.769
My organization has modern equipment/systems to serve customers.	.766
My organization has employees who understand the needs of customers.	.724
Explained variation	64.7
Eigenvalue	3.60
Cronbach's alpha	.868

Table 3. Correlations

		Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
1	Age ^b	4.26	.44	1									
2	Gender ^a	.54	.50	.054	1								
3	Education ^a	.21	.41	.242*	.177	1							
4	Tenure ^b	4.00	1.18	.403**	.307**	.231*	1						
5	Ownership ^a	.31	.47	.216	.141	.016	.000	1					
6	Industry presence ^b	5.39	1.49	.260*	.028	.084	.087	.264	1				
7	No. of employees ^b	6.25	1.43	.226*	.153	.170	.207*	.073	.538**	1			
8	Job related training	3.30	.72	.118	.256*	.011	.057	.039	.022	.113	1		
9	Talent engagement	3.59	.76	.092	.167	.161	.049	.045	.324**	.357**	.368**	1	
10	Quality of service	3.44	.68	.157	.143	.022	.369**	.037	.235*	.174	.382*	.479**	1

Notes: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables. ^b Log transformed

Table 4. Summary of results: structural model coefficients

Path	Standardized regression estimate (significance) Direct effect	Squared multiple correlation
Talent engagement ---> Quality of service	.283 (p<.05)	.358
Job related training ---> Quality of service	.217 (p<.10)	

Figures

Figure 1: P-P Plot of talent engagement (n=402)

Figure 2: P-P Plot of job related training (n=402)

Figure 3: P-P Plot of quality of service (n=402)

Figure 4: Partial regression plot – talent engagement and quality of service (n=402)

Figure 5: Partial regression plot – job related training and quality of service (n=402)